

St. John of Damascus Institute of Theology
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ANNALS

The Book of Joshua and the Gospels

روحانية البراري وروحانية المدن

Metamorphosis of the Lord Jesus Christ
according to St. John of Damascus

الملامح اللاهوتية للخبرة الروحية
ومعانيّة النور الإلهي

The Person & Work of Priests

ANNALS 9

Academic Year
2011-2012

THE BOOK OF JOSHUA AND THE GOSPELS INTERTEXTUALITY OF NARRATIVE AND MACRONARRATIVE PATTERNS (*)

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1. Introduction

The Book of Joshua has inspired different interpretations throughout Christian history. Joshua can be considered either as a master of ancient warfare or as a model of spiritual struggle. This book has been studied as a source for historians and archaeologists, who themselves have questioned to a large extent its historicity. But, what are the main meaning lines drawn in this book that expresses a particular vision of the early history of Israel at a critical time for the people who believed in the Lord, i.e., when they had experienced exile and had to restructure themselves in both the political and religious fields?

This paper deals with the Book of Joshua from a purely synchronic approach. First, we shall try to define the role that Joshua plays in the TANAKH canon because this will help to identify more clearly its role and its message. Afterward, two hermeneutical keys for the Book of Joshua will be discussed: the interpretation of battles and the taking possession of land. These two issues are critical especially for Arabic-speaking Christians and much more for Palestinian Christians. Finally, we move onto the main part of the article, which compares the Joshua narratives with the Jesus narratives in the canonical Gospels. These New Testament books make use of topics, motifs and narrative strategies from the Book of Joshua in order to portray Jesus' work.

In short, the Book of Joshua is part of the bi-testamentary Bible and,

(*) A shorter version of this paper has been presented in the conference **Violence in the name of God? Joshua in Changing Contexts**, which was organized by the WCC and its Palestine-Israel Encumenical Forum in collaboration with the EKD and the Evangelical Church in Kurhessen-Waldeck. The conference was held from 23 to 27 February 2012 at the Evangelical Academy of Hofgeismar, Germany.

therefore, it is an important element in the chain of revelation. No doubt that its place in the canon highlights it as a book of singular importance and that its common points with the Gospels, as we shall see, show its influence on the formation of Christian theology.

2. The Book of Joshua in the Canon

Modern literary criticism has observed that the place of Biblical books in the canon is important in the act of interpreting their texts. Brevard Childs said already in the 70's that "the traditions of the tradition have sought to hide their own footprints in order to focus attention on the canonical text itself and not on the process" (p. 32). Today, the canonical approach has become a synchronic method of interpretation that has enhanced its tools and has contributed with relevant fruits to Biblical research (see Noble).

The Book of Joshua has drawn the scholars' attention because of its place in the canon. Von Rad was one of the most prominent scholars, who by the year 1938 considered the existence of a Hexateuch. In this way, Joshua was understood as the triumphant conclusion of the promises in Genesis. However, from a canonical point of view, the Book of Joshua is the opening of the prophetic books, the *Nevi'im* in the Tanakh, which extend from Joshua to Malachi; but above all it is the opening of the Former Prophets (נביאים ראשונים *Nevi'im Rishonim*).¹ Therefore, rather than a conclusion, the book is to be understood as a triumphant genesis of the people of God's history presented precisely by the Deuteronomistic school and extended from Joshua till 2 Kings.

Certainly, the book of Joshua neither belongs to the narrative dynamics of the historical books, as we find them from Judges on, nor directly relates itself with the Pentateuch, especially because of the decisive changes of place and characters, as well as for the key turn in the narrative to enter the land. The tensions between Joshua and other historical books or between Joshua and modern history data sources ensure that Joshua cannot be read as a history book. Abadie

(1) The other collection of prophets would be the *Latter Prophets* (*Nevi'im Aharonim* נביאים אחרונים) which extends from Isaiah to Malachi.

offers a detailed list of these tensions (5-8). We will give here only a few examples. The first is, of course, the sharp contrast between the rapid conquest reports in Jos 1-12 and the more realistic ones of Judges, which highlight the difficulties they had to establish themselves in different regions. However, already the second part of Joshua expresses a different point of view, according to which each tribe seems to have committed themselves individually for the conquest of their own land (cf. 13:2-6, 15:13-19, 17:14.18; 19:47; 23:7-13). Two other examples demonstrate also these tensions. According to Jos 10:36, "Joshua and all Israel with him went up from Eglon to Hebron, and they fought against it". But this report contradicts another, much more likely in view of the geographical proximity, which affirms that the conquest of Hebron was achieved by the clan of Caleb (Jos 14:13 -15; 15:13 -14). Furthermore, according to 10:33 Joshua seized the city of Gezer, which will not enter under Israelite domain until Solomon's days, if we are to believe 1 King 9:16 (a fact that is, in its turn, very much discussed today). The Book of Joshua has also significant tensions with certain external sources such as the Amarna letters, which show a strong Egyptian presence in the area in a slightly earlier period (1300 BC) that goes completely unnoticed in the book.

In his introduction to the Old Testament, Erich Zenger said that the Pentateuch defines the history of God's people in this world (68). That is why the people of the desert have never entered the land. It is the story of their relationship with God, their sorrows, their faith, their doubts and their trust in the Lord. Starting from this premise it is understandable that the book of Joshua has a content of eschatological type. In other words, Joshua tells what is unrealizable to man and what is expected with faith and steadfastness that God shall fulfill one day. Thus, the reader of Joshua stands exactly between the glorious (and fictional) "past" of the story and the hope of entering the land to enjoy the promised goods. This way of reading Joshua links it directly with the book of Daniel that places the reader, who was under the yoke of the Seleucid (second century BC), between a hero from the Babylonian days called Daniel (sixth century BC) and the imminent coming of the Son of Man (Dan 7 and 9).

Crawford dedicated an article to the use of Joshua by Luke and

concluded that Joshua has relevant parallel elements with the Book of Acts. This can be very convincing if we study the book separately. In that case, Joshua is similar to Acts because of their common apocalyptic character and because Joshua is the disciple of Moses as much as the Apostles are Jesus' ones. However, there are two aspects that highlight the differences between these two books. On the one hand, Joshua holds a triumphant pace throughout the narrative, which can get extremely epic and legendary in some cases (see for instance the detention of the sun in Jos 10:13-14). This element is only present in the first chapters of Acts and then the church starts to suffer strong internal and external adversities. On the other hand, the book of Judges, with its ups and downs of the people's faith and loyalty shows a closer similarity with Acts.

Considering the diptych Joshua - Judges, it can be affirmed that Joshua is more like a Gospel while Judges is rather like Acts. It is in Judges where I rather see a parallelism with the book of Acts. Joshua is a special time where the communication between God and his people is functioning ideally (with the exception of the Achan episode in Jos 7). It narrates the eschatological fulfillment of the will of God and insofar, it is a book very similar to the Gospels. Many would ask at this moment about the role of the Torah. Actually, the Pentateuch has a unique place in the canon, which in many senses is not comparable to the Gospels themselves. The Books of Moses are the beginning and the principle even for the Gospels. Joshua comes as the ideal answer to the Pentateuch and this is why its canonical function is very similar to the Gospels'. The only element of the Gospels that make them have a similar function in the canon to the Pentateuch's one is the presence of a new revelation and a new covenant with God. However, even this crucial component of the New Testament theology comes as an answer to the Torah and not as an out-of-nothing substitute.

In conclusion, a perfect analogy between the New and Old Testament canons is impossible. Especially, because the New Testament canon was not written to abolish the former but to give it a continuation (cf. Mt 5:17). From a canonical point of view, the Torah is unique and is the beginning of the entire bi-testamentary Bible. In so far, the book of Joshua is to be considered more like a Gospel than like Acts, and this

because of two main reasons: first, the content of the narrative of the conquest of the land through an exemplary hero and, second, its strong accent on the apocalyptic fulfillment of the promise.

3. Who really fights in the Book of Joshua

Some modern approaches conceive the Old Testament history as constitutional narratives for a nation whose official religion is the worship of YHWH (Guillaume). This way of understanding the historical books limits the horizons of their prophetic content and reduces them to mere royal archives that record the official history of a monarchy that today does not even exist. It is inconceivable that the God of the Old Testament gave the people who just fled out of Egypt the privilege to have power over other nations and dominate the territories of other nations. In this case the Israel of the wilderness would be preparing to be a new Pharaoh and oppressor of nations.

An attentive and critical reading of Joshua shows clearly that the only one who fights in the battles is the Lord and that the role of the people is restricted to obeying God's commands (see, for example, the fall of Jericho in Jos 6; Achan's episode in Jos 7:8-12 and the rereading of the work of God in Jos 24:1-14). Therefore the people in Joshua do not run a war themselves, but rather they follow the Lord's instruction, who guides them into a new Land to bear witness of Him. The Biblical canon explains this function as a ministry and as a witness to the faith in the One and True God.

Chapter 10 narrates a series of battles in the land of Canaan. The inhabitants of Gibeon had made peace with Israel and lived among them (10:1). This fact already shows that the narrator neither aims at reporting the annihilation of all nations living in Canaan, nor records their subjugation, because the text clearly says "the inhabitants of Gibeon had made peace with Israel and were within their land," (v. 2). The text does not say "they were subdued" or "they lived under Israel's oppression." When the five kings of the Amorites organized themselves to attack Israel, which in this case also includes the nation of Gibeon (v. 5), it is God who fights in defense of them *all* (v. 10). The narrator concludes with a very special interpretive whisper: "And there was no

day like that before it or after it, when the Lord listened to the voice of a man; for **the Lord fought for Israel.**" (Jos 10:14).

Further in the text, in 10:42-43, we hear the narrator's final conclusions, where he summarizes all the achievements of Joshua (i.e. the Lord) in his battles: "And Joshua captured all these kings and their lands at one time, because the Lord, the God of Israel, fought for Israel. So, Joshua and all Israel with him returned to the camp at Gilgal." (Jos 10:42-43). Now, if one reads the Hebrew text, one can also translate: "And the Salvation of the Lord captured all these kings and their lands at one time, because the Lord, the God of Israel, fought for Israel. So the *Salvation of the Lord* and all Israel with it (the believers among whom there were also nations) returned to the camp at Gilgal." It means that the salvation expanded in all the Land and that the power of the Lord is known everywhere. Their function as true witnesses is working successfully. In this sense, it is God who really fights against apostasy and paganism. Men just obey His word. Otherwise, the whole struggle is lost. It is quite like Jesus, who follows verbatim the will of God (Mark 14:36par). In both books we find the fulfillment of God's suffering servant according to Isaiah 42ss. They do what God commands. Paragraph 5 shall develop this topic in a more extensive way.

4. Inheritance and possession in Conflict

From the text quoted above we can now move to another issue of great importance in the theology of Joshua: land possession. If we read 10:42 carefully, we see that the narrator says that it was the Lord who captured their lands (Hebrew: לָקַח). The text does not say that He **despoiled** the land from the nations, or that He gave the land in possession to Israel. The only one that behaves as a true landowner is God.²

Let us read an even more adverse text for this kind of interpretation, which is Jos 1:11: "Pass through the camp, and command the people: 'Prepare your provisions; for in three days you are to cross over the

(2) The well-known Arabic phrase *al-mulk li-Allah* (المالك لله) has always drawn my attention because it expresses a Semitic notion that is rarely perceived in the post-modern West. It means both, God is king and God is the only one who can possess. In this Semitic notion possession is no human business.

Jordan, to go in to take possession (Hebrew: לְרִשֵּׁת) of the land that the Lord your God gives you to possess (Hebrew: לְרִשְׁתָּהּ).”

Perhaps this text is one of the most difficult to prove that the notion of human possession is absent in Joshua. Precisely, the verb used in Hebrew here to say take possession is רִשָּׁה. The Septuagint translation for this verse provides for the first occurrence the verb κατέχω, which means *to keep, to have*, although it should be mentioned that most of the time the Septuagint translates it with κληρονομέω or its derivatives, which mean *to inherit* (Ayuch, 38 - 43). Clearly, modern translations reflect an important semantic problem here, to which I refer in an article published in Spain, where I show that the verb רִשָּׁה, in any of its forms has the sense of *inheriting* and not of *possessing*, when it takes the noun *land* as direct object (cf. Ayuch). What difference does it make? Well, a very important one, because Israel does not technically *take possession* but only *inherits* what belongs to God alone and, as long as God lives, the land does not belong to Israel but they are the promise holders for inheriting it one day. Israel lives on the land with God, but at any time they may revolt against God, then they will lose their heir rights and will be exposed to the power of the nations. The Book of Judges tells this part of the story, when the people disobey the word of God and bear the yoke of the nations (cf. Jdg 2:11-15).

Land possession, in the worldly sense of the word, does not exist for the faithful people of the Old Testament. God is the only one who possesses and the people are only His loyal stewards and His future heirs. Given these hermeneutical keys about the wars for land and land ownership, we can proceed to address the issue of common elements between Joshua and the canonical Gospels.

5. Joshua's narrative elements common to the Gospels

A macronarrative study can clearly show how the Gospel writers take topoi, motifs and narrative strategies of Joshua to present Jesus of Nazareth. In general lines, one can see two macronarrative motifs that dominate the book of Joshua and have clearly been taken by the Evangelists: The land conquest and the promise fulfillment by the deeds of two protagonists: Joshua and Jesus.

As for the conquest, it is carried out in Joshua following the proper rules of the narrative according to the role of the book in the Deuteronomistic history. That is why we find etiological scenes and epics (to follow Martin Noth's terminology), which speak of a primeval time that exists in the collective memory as an ideal period that generates the community's identity. In this sense we can mention the story of the twelve memorial stones (Jos 4:1-9) and the construction of the altar on Mount Ebal (8:30-35).

As for the promise fulfillment, the book of Joshua professes that salvation is possible and that the chosen people will rejoice. This is what happened in the beginning and so, therefore, will have to happen at the end of time. The book starts with the mention of a promise that will be fulfilled with the help of Joshua (1:2-5). Once it is fulfilled, Joshua disappears (24:29-31). In the Gospels, this fulfillment notion is essential (Perhaps Matthew uses it more explicitly than the other three with his introductions to the OT quotations "this is to fulfill..."; see Mt 1:22; 4:14). This concept is rather an apocalyptic one. The apocalyptic tone is marked even more after the emergence of this literature that influences the four Evangelists. But you cannot deny that the seeds of this literature are already present in Joshua when the narrative depicts the old times. Or is not the vision of Adam and Eve in paradise also an apocalyptic one? (cf. Karl Löning, who argues that the discourses on the origins and the end are similar in form and motifs).

Going into the narrative strategy, we see that the Book of Joshua is clearly of two well defined stages: the stage of the conquest (1-12) and the stage of land distribution (13-22). The Gospels also have these two moments, these two plots, called the Galilee time (Mark 1-8, Luke 1-9; Mt 1-18) and the Jerusalem time (Mark 8-16, Luke 9-24; Mt 19-28).³ Finally the book of Joshua concludes with two farewell addresses of Joshua before his death, during which a covenant is cut between the

(3) In John, this division takes place between the Book of the Seven Signs (1-11) and the Book of the Hour (12-20). Matthew could be considered as the one who reflects the least this bipartite structure, since his work highlights the five sermons, which are scattered throughout the book. However, Mt 19:1 is clear and concise: "And it came about that when Jesus had finished these words, He departed from Galilee, and came into the region of Judea beyond the Jordan".

tribes and their God (Jos 23-24). These scenes inspire the most decisive moments of the New Covenant foundation. They are also interlinked with the concluding words of Jesus at the end of Matthew and Luke (Mt 28:18-20; Lk 24:47-49).

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Turning now to specific narrative topoi that prove the intertextuality between Joshua and the Gospels we can mention as a first scene the crossing of the Jordan for the beginning of the conquest. Undoubtedly, the passage of the river Jordan in 3:14-17 evokes the crossing of the Red Sea "standing firm on dry ground" (v. 17 cf. Ex 14:29-30) and the Evangelists take it as a model for the Baptism of Jesus (Mark 1:9-11, Matthew 3:13-17, Luke 3:21-22, John 1:29-34). On the one hand, God's authority is present in Joshua through the Ark of the Covenant; the ark is His will and His Word, which allows the people to cross the river. The narrator says carefully that "the ark of the covenant (went) before the people" (v. 14) and that the priests were standing firm because they carried the ark (v. 17). On the other hand, God is present in the Gospels in a cosmic event with loud voice manifesting His will. Here Jesus is Joshua and the people at once. He is the chosen one who goes out to rescue the lost of Israel (Mk 1:11, Lk 3:22, Mt 3:17).

Redemption happens in both books in the same way: by unconditional obedience to the Lord (the Law and the words of Moses in Joshua; the will of the Father in the Gospels) and by fighting against evil. Jesus defeats all the evil that has possessed men in sickness and that symbolically means disobedience to the word of God. Joshua fights against cultures and beliefs that are far from the One True God. He guides the people to a society with a new faith. In Jos 24 the ones in the meeting are not just those who came out from Egypt but all the inhabitants of the land, including all nations that accepted Joshua. The Last Supper scenes in the Gospels recall the concluding covenant of Shechem in Jos 24.

Another of the scenes that clearly evokes the book of Joshua in the Gospels is Jesus' passing through Jericho before entering Jerusalem (Mk 10:46-52, Lk 18:35-43, Mt 20:29-34). The "conquest of Jericho" in this case does not go through the miraculous bringing down of the

city walls but by restoring the Jewish people's sense of sight. In the Gospels, the Jews must first recover that ancient sight power that they used to have in Joshua's days in order to understand Jesus and then to be able to proclaim the Gospel to the Nations. The blind man exclaims: "Jesus, Son of David, have mercy on me" (Mk 10:47, Lk 18:38, Mt 20:30) and thus clearly defines his Jewish faith.

Once Jesus gives sight back to his people, he goes to Jerusalem to proclaim there a New Covenant and open up salvation to all nations, just as in the Book of Joshua, where salvation is open to every nation that accepts the faith in the Lord of Israel. One of the most important examples is the story of Rahab that extends from chapter 2 to the happy ending of 6:25: "However, Rahab the harlot and her father's household and all she had, Joshua spared; and she has lived in the midst of Israel to this day, for she hid the messengers whom Joshua sent to spy out Jericho." Another aspect of great importance in Joshua's macronarrative that ensures salvation to all nations is the fact that the people who crossed the Jordan River with the leading of the Lord's Ark were **uncircumcised**. Indeed, the river crossing is done in Chapter 3 (see in particular v. 17), while the circumcision is first done in 5:2-9. Only then can the people celebrate the Pesach (5:10-12). This new generation of people was born in the desert, in no man's land and along the way (5:5). Because of their ancestors' disobedience they had not received the grace of circumcision. Once they were circumcised, the Lord removed them "the reproach of Egypt" (5:9). The word reproach (תקפה) is important in the Old Testament and indicates the nations' submission to their gods (see Hamlin 34-35). Therefore, the conquest of Jericho is conditioned by the acceptance of faith.

Another evident topos of intertextuality that has a less narrative aspect is the name of both characters, which is the same *Iesous* (Ἰησοῦς) in Greek as translated by the Septuagint and the New Testament original text. Some Evangelists explain the meaning of the name in the way Sirach does in the opening of a hymn of praise to the works of Joshua (46:1-10). The text of Sirach is not only important as a link to the meaning of the name but also as an interpretation of the stories in Joshua: "his name was made great for the saving of the elect of God, and taking vengeance on the enemies that rose up against them, that he

might set Israel in their inheritance." Jesus in the Gospels has this Savior feature (σωτήρ) and he announces the coming of the Kingdom, which is the true inheritance of the elect and believers. The most representative texts we can mention here are:

"Blessed are the poor in spirit, for theirs is the kingdom of heaven."
(Mt 5:3)

"...and they were saying to the woman, 'It is no longer because of what you said that we believe, for we have heard for ourselves and know that this One is indeed the Savior of the world.'" (Jn 4:42)

"For today in the city of David there has been born for you a Savior, who is Christ the Lord." (Lk 2:11)

Of course, this aspect of Jesus' character is more developed in the Gospels than in the book of Joshua and the titles given to him and his authority are by far superior to the ones given to Joshua. However, this does not deny that several literary motifs and narrative functions of Joshua have either inspired the Evangelists, or at least find an echo in the New Testament text.

Absolute obedience to the Lord's will is one of the theological fundamentals of Joshua as a narrative character. This happens repeatedly in the book and it is the key to his success. Since the beginning of the book God speaks directly to Joshua saying:

"Only be strong and very courageous; be careful to do according to all the law which Moses my servant commanded you; do not turn from it to the right or to the left, so that you may have success wherever you go. 8This book of the law shall not depart from your mouth, but you shall meditate on it day and night, so that you may be careful to do according to all that is written in it; for then you will make your way prosperous, and then you will have success. 9Have I not commanded you? Be strong and courageous! Do not tremble or be dismayed, for the LORD your God is with you wherever you go." (Jos 1:7-9)

Joshua must obey **all** the **Law**, never step away from this book and so he will succeed in everything he does. In Joshua 4:10 the people and

the priests do "all that the Lord commanded." In 11:9 it says literally that Joshua did as the Lord commanded him: "and Joshua did to them as the LORD had told him". In 11:15 the narrator highlights an even more humble obedience because Joshua obeys Moses and, through him, God: "Just as the Lord had commanded Moses his servant, so Moses commanded Joshua, and so Joshua did; he left nothing undone of all that the Lord had commanded Moses. (Jos 11:15)"

Jesus' obedience is also a central theme in the Gospels and it is manifested in several ways: through his sayings, the stories, and the fulfillment of Scriptures, among which the motif of Isaiah's Suffering Servant, who obeys the Lord to death, is the most relevant one. Here I choose four quotations to mention a few:

- "...and behold, a voice out of the heavens, saying, "This is my beloved Son, in whom I am well-pleased." (Mt 3:17)
- "And He who sent me is with me; He has not left me alone, for I always do the things that are pleasing to Him." (Jn 8:29)
- "And He was saying, Abba! Father! All things are possible for Thee; remove this cup from me; yet not what I will, but what Thou wilt." (Mk 14:36)
- "And it was at this time that He went off to the mountain to pray, and He spent the whole night in prayer to God." (Lk 6:12)

But the issue does not only have to do with obedience but also with submission and humility; that humility about which Paul speaks in Phil 2:3 and which inspires the whole Servant Hymn. The best example of Joshua's humility is perhaps that in the entire book he is not called "servant of the Lord," as Moses was (cf. Jos 1:2,13; 8:31; 11:12; 13:8; 22:5). Only at the time of his death the narrator calls him a servant, i.e., when he has accomplished his mission. It is noteworthy to mention that the most common expression in Greek for Moses is Μωσῆς ὁ παῖς κυρίου (Jos 1:13), while for Joshua is Ἰησοῦς υἱὸς Ναη δοῦλος κυρίου (Jos 24:30). This latter is the favorite word of Paul to define his relationship with God. The term *paî`ò* is used in the Gospels to talk about Jesus. In any case, the Hebrew term is only one: יְהוָה.

Another common theme between the two *Iesous* is the emergence

of a follower with other plans, somebody who has another point of view, a real *diabolos*, in the literal sense of the Greek word. These two characters appear in this role shortly after the "conquest" of Jericho. One of them is Achan of the tribe of Judah (Jos 7:1) and, of course, Judas Iscariot (Mark 14:10-11, Luke 22:3-6, Mt 26:14-16). The intention of both traitors is understood from the context of the story: Both of them choose to rely on human power rather than on God's plans. That is why Achan is accused of transgressing the covenant of the LORD, and committing a disgraceful thing in Israel (Jos 7:15b). Judas, in his turn, believes more in the Temple priests than in his own Master, who had openly stated his opposition to the institution (cf. Mk 11:11.15-18, Lk 19:45-46, Mt 21:12-17).

The four Gospels present Jesus in his mission of conquering the land. This is precisely what he does with his proclamation throughout Galilee and later on his way to Jerusalem. This is one of the main points in this book comparison. Jesus conquered the land preaching and this is exactly what the Book of Joshua also presents. Joshua conquered the land with the belief in One God. Through the symbolism of war and the defeat of one nation to another, the book shows that the truth of the One God can overcome the ones who believe in the pagan gods, who actually do not exist and therefore must lose the war. The book deals with the spreading of the faith in the One God all over the "land", i.e., among the nations. This is why it can be read as an eschatological discourse.

6. Conclusions

Who exercises power? Who is the first one? Who is the chosen one? Who rules? These are issues that are present from the scene of the fall (the power struggle between man and God), passing through the scenes of Cain and Abel (the fight between brothers), Isaac and Esau (two nations), Saul and David (two kings), up to the disciples of Jesus in the New Testament who also showed their interest for power (10:35 Mc-45par and Acts 1:6-7). The man's eternal struggle for power is reflected in the whole history of salvation. The Bible always says 'no' to settlement in cities (Babel), 'no' to realms and kingdoms (deuteronomistic history), 'no' to worldly power (the prophets).

According to the Bible human beings are all under God's care and there is no need to draw borders to live in peace. The principle of coexistence given through revelation is far more tolerant than the one given by any secular philosophy. The biblical revelation affirms that all human beings belong to one family and that, therefore, everyone works and acts for the welfare of the community that they form and for the welfare of each individual. This is what the Law reveals with the principle of neighborly love at the heart of the Pentateuch: "You shall not take vengeance or bear a grudge against any of your people, but you shall love your neighbor as yourself: I am the Lord" (Lev 19:18). This is also what the narratives and prophetic books of the Old Testament teach by defending the poor and the oppressed and by rebuking the oppressors and powerful ones. The Ps 37:14-17 sums it up clearly: "The wicked draw the sword and bend their bows to bring down the poor and needy, to kill those who walk uprightly; their sword shall enter their own heart, and their bows shall be broken. Better is a little that the righteous person has than the abundance of many wicked. For the arms of the wicked shall be broken, but the Lord upholds the righteous."

This comparison between the narratives of Joshua and the Gospels and these reflections are proposed to understand the Book of Joshua from a Christian perspective and by approaching the Biblical canon from a mere Christian point of view. It investigated the way the Book of Joshua influenced the Evangelists and, therefore, how early Christians interpreted this book.

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